

Antidyslipidemic Effect of A Newly Synthesized Metformin - Resveratrol Aldehyde Complex in High Fat Diet Fed- Low Dose Streptozotocin-Induced Experimental Type 2 Diabetes in Rats

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ABSTRACT

Diabetic dyslipidemia, clinically defined as atherogenic dyslipidemia, is established to be primarily responsible for the increased cardiovascular complications in diabetes mellitus that are attributed to a definite insulin deficiency (Type 1) or the diminished ability of insulin to act effectively on target tissues such as muscle, liver, and fat (Type 2). An active compound, Metformin - Resveratrol Aldehyde Complex (Met- Res - Aldehyde complex), has been designed, synthesized, and characterized by spectral studies, and its toxic as well as optimum therapeutic dose have been reported by us. Subsequent to *in silico* as well as *in vitro* evaluation of its hypoglycemic properties, the effect of oral administration of the complex in the regulation of carbohydrate metabolism in high fat diet fed-low dose streptozotocin - induced experimental type 2 diabetic rats was reported recently. In the present study, we have investigated the effect of the newly synthesized complex on serum as well as tissue lipid profiles in experimental type 2 diabetic rats. The diabetic rats were treated with Met-Res-Aldehyde complex (5 mg/kg b.w./rat/day) for 30 days. The levels of total cholesterol, triglycerides, free fatty acids and phospholipids were assayed in the serum, besides lipoprotein (high-density lipoprotein-cholesterol (HDL), low-density lipoprotein-cholesterol (LDL) and very low-density lipoprotein-cholesterol (VLDL)) in liver and kidney tissues. Total cholesterol, triglycerides, free fatty acids, phospholipids, LDL and VLDL levels were increased in serum and tissues significantly, whereas serum HDL significantly decreased in diabetic rats. The decreased levels of adiponectin and increased levels of leptin in the plasma of diabetic rats reverted to their physiological range after treatment with the complex for 30 days. Treatment with the newly synthesized Met-Res-Aldehyde complex reversed the above-mentioned alterations and improved towards normalcy. Thus, administration of Met-Res-Aldehyde complex is able to control both chronic hyperglycemia and hyperlipidemia related to the risk of development of cardiovascular complications in experimental type 2 diabetes in rats.

Keywords: Met-Res-Aldehyde complex, Antidyslipidemic property, insulin mimetic property.

INTRODUCTION

Diabetes mellitus (DM) is a group of chronic metabolic disorders that are attributed to a definite or relative insulin deficiency (Type 1) or the diminished ability of insulin to act effectively on target tissues such as muscle, liver and fat (Type 2). Type 2 diabetes constitutes more than 95% of the total diabetic

population in the world and is characterized by insulin resistance coupled with a deficiency of insulin secretion that is characterized by metabolic disorders of lipids, carbohydrates, and proteins [1, 2]. According to the International Diabetes Federation (IDF) report for the year 2025, currently 589 million people aged between 20-79 years were living with DM in 2024, around 11.1% of the world's population

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in this age group, and it is projected that by the year 2050, based just on future trends in population growth, population aging, and urbanization, diabetes cases will increase to 853 million people; about 45% worldwide will be affected by DM [3]. The primary cause is either a disruption in insulin secretion, varying degrees of insulin resistance, or, more commonly, a combination of both [4, 5].

Both chronic hyperglycemia and hyperlipidemia share most of the common clinical features contributing to the initiation, progression, and onset of microvascular as well as macrovascular complications of diabetes mellitus [6,7]. Diabetes mellitus, if undiagnosed over a longer period, or inadequately treated, is most often correlated with the increased risk of cardiovascular diseases, kidney disorders, blindness, and foot amputation [8-11]. Chronic hyperglycemia predisposes to cardiovascular diseases (CVD), making CVD one of the leading causes of morbidity and mortality in diabetic individuals. Dyslipidemia is the most important and modifiable risk factor for CVDs, probably due to the Westernization of diet, reduced physical activity, and urbanization as well as the development of central obesity. Diabetic dyslipidemia is a cluster of plasma lipid and lipoprotein abnormalities that are metabolically interrelated and defined by a decrease in high-density lipoprotein (HDL) cholesterol, an increase in triglyceride (TG) levels, and a mild effect on low-density lipoprotein (LDL) cholesterol and central obesity [12-14]. High levels of TGs or low levels of HDL-C or both have been identified in more than half of the subjects with T2DM [15,16]. An early major contributor to the development of insulin resistance is an circulating free fatty acids (FFAs) that are released from expanded adipose tissue triglyceride (TG) stores through the lipolysis of TG-rich lipoproteins in tissues by lipoprotein lipase [17,18]. In the liver, increased levels of FFAs result in an increased production of glucose and TGs; secretion of overabundance of VLDL-C and LDL-C; as well as a reduction of HDL-C [19, 20]. FFAs also reduce insulin sensitivity in muscle tissue by inhibiting insulin-mediated glucose uptake, and FFA flux to the liver is associated with the increased production of TG-rich VLDL-C [21, 22].

Rigorous control of blood glucose levels in patients with diabetes is of key importance in reducing the risk of developing lipid-cardiovascular complications. Lifestyle measures and intensive drug therapy are crucial to aggressively treat these risk factors of dyslipidemia in patients with DM. Pharmacological treatment approaches for diabetic dyslipidemia include both glucose- and lipid-lowering drugs. The accessible medications for diabetes are insulin and varied oral antidiabetic agents having different mechanisms of action, such as biguanides, sulfonylureas, thiazolidinediones, non-sulfonylureas secretagogues, and α -glucosidase inhibitors, etc. [23-25]. These drugs are used as either monotherapy or combined to get better glycemic control and mask serious adverse effects of each oral antidiabetic agent [26,27]. Though drugs are plentiful for the treatment of chronic hyperglycemia associated with hyperlipidemia, none is found to have the expected efficacy. One of the major advances in cardiovascular management is the discovery of statins. The scientific community beams with evidence of the lowering of serum cholesterol with statins that is eventually associated with decreased risk of CHD. However, the use of statins is associated with various side effects despite their positive effects on the plasma lipid profile; among these, statins might cause a disruption of a number of regulatory pathways, including insulin signaling. This may affect insulin sensitivity, pancreatic β -cell function, and adipokine secretion [28, 29].

Some therapies used to improve glycemic control in diabetic patients may have an impact on lipid levels above and beyond their effects on glucose metabolism. In reviewing the literature, it is frequently very hard to separate improvements in glycemic control from direct effects of drugs. Additionally, many of the changes induced by drug therapy result in only small changes in LDL-C, HDL-C and TG levels, are variable from study to study, and are of questionable clinical significance. Metformin has been prescribed as a first-line pharmacotherapy in diabetes for more than 50 years [30,31] and is currently considered the essential drug for the treatment of T2DM patients and the backbone for combination therapy [32,33]. It was added to the WHO's essential medicines list in the year 2011 [34,35]. Metformin may decrease serum TG levels

and LDL-C levels without altering HDL-C levels [36,37]. In contrast, metformin did not significantly alter HDL-C levels [38,39]. It should be noted that in the Diabetes Prevention Program, [40] individuals with impaired glucose metabolism were randomized to placebo, intensive lifestyle, or metformin therapy. In the metformin therapy group no significant changes were noted in TG, LDL-C, or HDL-C levels compared to the placebo group [41, 42]. Thus, metformin may have small effects on lipid levels. Further, metformin possesses several undesirable side effects (from mild to severe) that cause lack of adherence, and therefore it is considered an oral antidiabetic drug with the lowest compliance [43,44]. During research into developing synthetic therapeutics for diabetes, several complexes have been found to exhibit hypoglycemic and hypolipidemic effects in animals and humans [45,46]. The increasing knowledge of the biological activities of simple complexes guided many researchers to the development of promising chemotherapeutic compounds, which target specific pathological processes. These studies involve synthetic complexes, in association with essential complexes.

Resveratrol is a non-flavonoid polyphenolic compound. Structurally, it is a 3, 5, 4'-trihydroxystilbene. Dietary sources of resveratrol include grapes, peanuts, cocoa, and a large range of fruits, including bilberry, cranberry, and blueberry [47,48]. Resveratrol was synthesized naturally by 70 different plant species, and it was first identified in 1940 from the white *hellobore lily* *Veratrum grandiflorum* O. Loes [49-51]. However, the occurrence was popularized in 1992, when it was discovered as an indispensable constituent of red wine and implicated in the "French Paradox," an epidemiological finding of an inverse relationship between red wine consumption and incidence of heart diseases [52-54]. Earlier, we reported the antidiabetic efficacy of resveratrol in experimental type 2 diabetes in rats. We have also reported the effect of oral administration of resveratrol at a concentration of 5 mg/kg. b.w./rat/ for 30 days to experimental type 2 diabetes in attenuating the activities of key regulatory enzymes of carbohydrate metabolism [55]. We have also reported the ameliorative potential of diabetic dyslipidemia, hyperglycemia-induced oxidative stress, and pancreatic tissue protective nature [56-59].

Recently, we have reported a review on the beneficial and pharmacological properties of resveratrol [60].

Having these beneficial as well as pharmacological efficacies of metformin and resveratrol, we have synthesized a new metformin-resveratrol-aldehyde complex as an organic ligand and characterized its structure using various spectral studies. We have also evaluated its glucose uptake efficacy using rat L6 skeletal muscle cell lines [61]. We have also studied the molecular docking and simulation of the antidiabetic activity of the resveratrol aldehyde molecule [62]. Likewise, we have also reported the molecular docking of the synthesized resveratrol molecule against type 2 diabetic target proteins [63]. More recently, we have reported the biochemical evaluation of the antidiabetic efficacy of the metformin-resveratrol aldehyde complex in high-fat diet-fed, low-dose streptozotocin-induced experimental type 2 diabetes in rats [64]. In the present study, an attempt has been made to explore the antidyslipidemic effect of the metformin-resveratrol-aldehyde complex in streptozotocin-induced diabetic rats.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Chemicals

Resveratrol, metformin, streptozotocin, and Insulin were obtained from Sigma Aldrich, USA. An ultra-sensitive ELISA kit for rat insulin assay was purchased from Crystal Chem Inc. Life Technologies, India. All the other chemicals and reagents used were of analytical grade.

Synthesis of Resveratrol aldehyde

Resveratrol aldehyde (RA) (2,4-dihydroxy-6-((E)-2-(4 hydroxyphenyl)) benzaldehyde) was synthesized by the methods of [65,66]. Resveratrol was treated with Vilsmeier reagent (POCl₃, DMF, and MeCN) to synthesize resveratrol aldehyde. Briefly, freshly distilled POCl₃ (0.6 ml, 6 mmol) was added drop wise to a solution of resveratrol (912 mg, 4 mmol) and DMF (464 ml, 6 mmol) in 20 ml of MeCN that was maintained in an ice water bath. The mixture was stirred continuously for 1 hr. at room temperature. Then, the solution was added to a mixture of ice and water, and the yellow mixture was stirred at 40°C in a

water bath and extracted with EtOAc (3×10 ml) and evaporated. The yellow-colored crystals of RA were obtained with a yield of 78%. The overall scheme is represented as Scheme 1.

Scheme 1: Synthesis of Resveratrol Aldehyde

Synthesis of a mixed ligand from Metformin hydrochloride and Resveratrol Aldehyde (M-RA) Mixed ligand 4-(E)-((amino(E)-(2,4-dihydroxy-6-(4-hydroxyphenethyl)benzylidene) amino) (dimethylamine)methyl) amino) methyl) amino) methyl)-5-(4-hydroxyphenethyl)benzene-1,3-diol was prepared by refluxing the mixture of 1 mmol (0.2 g) of metformin with 2 mmol (0.5 g) of Resveratrol aldehyde in 50 ml methanol for about 6 hours. The pale-yellow-colored compound was dried, and the yield was 92 mg (72%). The proposed scheme is represented in Scheme 2.

Scheme 2: Synthesis of Metformin-Resveratrol Aldehyde mixed ligand.

The physico-chemical parameters of resveratrol aldehyde and metformin-resveratrol aldehyde mixed ligand were recorded. The resveratrol aldehyde and the mixed ligand were subjected to spectral characterization by FT-IR, ^1H NMR, ^{13}C NMR, and mass spectral analysis [61].

Experimental Animals

Male Albino rats of Wistar weighing around 160 to 180 g were procured from the Tamilnadu Veterinary and Animal Sciences University, Chennai, and were

housed in the Biomedical Research Unit and Lab Animal Centre, Saveetha Dental College and Hospitals, Chennai, under standard husbandry conditions (12 ± 1 h light and dark cycle, relative humidity $55\% \pm 10\%$). The animals were fed a balanced diet (Hindustan Lever Ltd., Bangalore, India) and water *ad libitum*. The rat pellet diet is composed of 55% nitrogen-free extract, 21% protein, 5% fat, and 4% fiber (w/w) with sufficient levels of vitamins and minerals. The experimental design was strictly conducted according to the ethical norms approved by the Ministry of Social Justice and Empowerment, Government of India, and Institutional Animal Ethics Committee Guidelines (Approval number - BRULAC/SDCH/SIMATS/IAEC/08-2022/137) for the examination of experimental pain in conscious animals.

The High Fat Diet (HFD) was prepared indigenously by using a normal pellet diet, raw cholesterol, and a mixture of Vanaspati ghee and pure coconut oil (2:1). Briefly, the normal rat pellet diet was powdered by grinding and mixed with 2.5% cholesterol and a mixture of Vanaspati ghee and coconut oil (5%). The mixture was made into pellet form and orally fed to rats to induce metabolic syndrome [67,68]. The rats were divided into two dietary regimens by feeding either normal or HFD for the initial period of 2 weeks. After 2 weeks of dietary management to develop insulin resistance, the groups of rats fed with HFD were intraperitoneally injected with a freshly prepared low dose of STZ (35 mg/kg b.w.) dissolved in 0.1M ice-cold citrate buffer, pH 4.5 [69,70]. Rats having the fasting blood glucose levels ≥ 300 mg/dL on the 3rd day after STZ injection were considered diabetic and subjected to further studies. The rats were allowed to continue to feed on their respective diets until the end of the experimental period.

Acute Toxicity and Dosage Fixation Studies

Acute toxicity studies were performed as per OECD guidelines for testing of chemicals in normal rats. Graded doses (2.5 mg, 5 mg, 7.5 mg, and 10 mg/kg b.w./rat) of the Met-Res-Aldehyde complex dissolved in 5% DMSO were orally administered to rats. The changes in food consumption, fluid intake, psychomotor activities, and body weight gain and

changes in skin, fur, eyes, salivation, diarrhea, and lethargy in rats were continuously monitored for a period of 30 days. Macroscopic examinations were also performed on vital organs. Oral administration of graded doses of the Met-Res-Aldehyde complex (5 mg/kg b.w./rat/day) for 30 days was performed to determine the dose-dependent hypoglycemic effect in HFD-low-dose STZ-induced diabetic rats by monitoring the fasting blood glucose levels periodically to fix the effective dose of the Met-Res-Aldehyde complex for treatment. Based on the results obtained, the optimum dose was fixed as 5 mg/kg. b.w./rat/day for 30 days for the present study.

Induction of experimental Type 2 diabetes in rats

The rats were allocated into two dietary regimens by feeding either a normal pellet diet (NPD) or a high-fat diet (HFD) for 2 weeks of dietary manipulation [71]. After 2 weeks of HFD supplementation to induce insulin resistance, the group of rats fed with HFD was intraperitoneally administered a low dose of STZ (35 mg/kg b.w. /rat) dissolved in 0.1 M ice-cold citrate buffer, pH 4.5 [69, 72, 73]. Control rats (Group I) fed with NPD were injected intraperitoneally with the same volume of freshly prepared cold citrate buffer (pH 4.5). After one week of STZ injection, rats having fasting blood glucose levels ≥ 300 mg/dL were considered diabetic rats and chosen for further studies.

The animals were divided into four groups, each comprising six rats as follows:

- Group 1 : Control.
- Group 2 : HFD+STZ induced experimental type 2 diabetic rats.
- Group 3 : HFD+STZ-induced diabetic rats treated with Met-Res-Aldehyde complex (5 mg/kg b.w./rat/day) for 30 days.
- Group 4 : HFD+STZ-induced diabetic rats treated with metformin 500 mg/kg b.w./rat/day for 30 days.

Biochemical Parameters

At the end of the experimental period, overnight fasted rats were anaesthetized, using ketamine (80 mg/kg b.w./rat) and sacrificed by cervical decapitation. Blood samples were collected with and without anticoagulant for separation of plasma and serum, respectively. The basic biochemical parameters such as fasting blood glucose [74,75], glycosylated hemoglobin [76,77], plasma protein [78,79], blood urea [80,81] and serum creatinine [82,83] levels were estimated. Urine strips were used to detect the presence of glucose in urine. The levels of plasma insulin were assayed by ELISA using a rat insulin assay kit (Linco Research, St. Charles, MO, USA).

Assay of lipid profile

The lipids were extracted from the liver and kidney tissues by the method of Folch *et al.*, (1957) [84,85]. The cholesterol and triglyceride contents were estimated by the methods of Parekh and Jung (1970) [86, 87] and Foster and Dunn (1973) [88,89] respectively. The free fatty acid contents in serum, liver, and kidney tissues were estimated by the method of Hron and Menahan (1981) [90,91]. High-density lipoproteins (HDL) and low-density lipoproteins (LDL) were separated from the serum according to the dual precipitation technique [92, 93] and the cholesterol content of the lipoproteins was estimated.

Statistical Analysis

The values are expressed as mean values of six rats in each group \pm SEM. Data analysis was done with SPSS software. The hypothesis testing method included one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) followed by post hoc testing performed with least significant difference (LSD). The value of $P < 0.05$ was considered to indicate statistical significance.

RESULTS

The effect of oral administration of Met-Res-Aldehyde complex at a concentration of 5 mg/kg/bw/rat/day for 30 days on the levels of fasting blood glucose, plasma insulin, glycosylated Hb, protein, urea, creatinine, and urine sugar in experimental type 2 diabetic rats is presented in Table 1. In the diabetic group of rats, the levels of fasting

blood glucose, HbA1c, urea, and creatinine were significantly increased, and the levels of plasma insulin and protein were decreased. Treatment with Met-Res-Aldehyde complex as well as metformin brought the altered levels of the above biochemical

indices to physiological values. The urine sugar, which was present in the diabetic group of rats, was absent in experimental groups of rats treated with the Met-Res-Aldehyde complex.

Table-1: Levels of blood glucose, plasma insulin, glycosylated Hb, protein, Urea, Creatinine and urine sugar in control and experimental groups of rats.

Groups	Control	Diabetic	Diabetic + Met - Res - Aldehyde complex	Diabetic + Metformin
Blood Glucose	93.88 ± 1.67 ^a	240 ± 12.90 ^b	114.66 ± 1.25 ^c	110.16 ± 2.83 ^c
Plasma Insulin	1.13 ± 0.17 ^a	0.3 ± 0.04 ^b	0.718 ± 0.05 ^c	0.83 ± 0.02 ^{ac}
Glycosylated Hb	4.19 ± 0.06 ^a	7.69 ± 0.10 ^b	6.1 ± 0.08 ^c	5.9 ± 0.05 ^c
Protein	7.90 ± 0.24 ^a	5.37 ± 0.23 ^b	6.25 ± 0.17 ^c	7.16 ± 0.13 ^a
Urea	8.92 ± 0.27 ^a	30.12 ± 1.64 ^b	18.36 ± 0.84 ^c	17.23 ± 0.90 ^c
Creatinine	0.95 ± 0.01 ^a	2.1 ± 0.14 ^b	1.28 ± 0.10 ^a	1.35 ± 0.13 ^a
Urine Sugar	Nil	+++	Nil	Nil

Units are expressed as mg/dL for blood glucose, ng/ml for plasma insulin, % hemoglobin for HbA1c, g/dL for plasma protein, mg/dL for blood urea and serum creatinine and +++ indicates more than 2% sugar. Results are expressed as mean ± S.E.M [n=6]. One-way ANOVA followed by post hoc test LSD. In each rows, means with different superscript letters differ significantly at p < 0.05.

The effect of oral administration of Met-Res-Aldehyde complex on the serum levels of total cholesterol, triglycerides, free fatty acids and phospholipids in the experimental groups of rats is

Table-2: The levels of Total Cholesterol, Triglycerides, Free fatty acids and Phospholipids in serum of control and experimental groups of rats.

Groups	Total Cholesterol	Triglycerides	Free fatty Acids	Phospholipids
Control	159.79 ± 3.02 ^a	119.21 ± 3.63 ^a	61.15 ± 1.29 ^a	76.77 ± 1.07 ^a
Diabetic	257.98 ± 5.85 ^b	194.06 ± 2.38 ^b	141.98 ± 1.11 ^b	153.15 ± 1.32 ^b
Diabetic + Met-Res-Aldehyde complex	170.99 ± 4.79 ^{ac}	129.75 ± 2.11 ^c	94.73 ± 1.18 ^c	109.88 ± 1.25 ^c
Diabetic + Metformin	182.88 ± 2.15 ^c	108.5 ± 1.88 ^c	99.19 ± 0.19 ^d	104.35 ± 2.67 ^c

represented in Table 2. The levels of the lipids were significantly elevated in the diabetic group of rats. Oral treatment with the newly synthesized complex significantly restored the altered levels to physiological levels when compared to the diabetic group of rats. The efficacy was comparable with the metformin-treated group of rats.

Units are expressed as mg/dL. Values are expressed as mean \pm S.E.M [n=6]. One-way ANOVA followed by post hoc test LSD. The Means with different superscript letters within the same column differ significantly at $p < 0.05$.

Table 3 depicts the effects of Met-Res- Aldehyde complex on the levels of cholesterol, triglycerides,

free fatty acids and phospholipids in the liver tissue of experimental groups of rats. The levels were significantly elevated in the diabetic group of rats when compared with the control group of rats. Oral administration of Met-Res- Aldehyde complex to diabetic groups of rats significantly improved these altered levels compared to diabetic rats.

Table-3 :The effect of Met-Res- Aldehyde complex treatment on the hepatic tissues of Total Cholesterol, Triglycerides, Free fatty acids and Phospholipids in the experimental groups of rats.

Groups	Total Cholesterol	Triglycerides	Free fatty acids	Phospholipids
Control	6.91 \pm 0.47 ^a	3.38 \pm 0.29 ^a	6.94 \pm 0.14 ^a	25.23 \pm 1.19 ^a
Diabetic	16.23 \pm 1.17 ^b	7.13 \pm 0.31 ^{bc}	12.24 \pm 0.43 ^b	43.21 \pm 1.33 ^b
Diabetic + Met-Res- Aldehyde complex.	10.6 \pm 0.66 ^c	5.43 \pm 0.32 ^c	8.20 \pm 0.50 ^{ac}	26.83 \pm 1.14 ^a
Diabetic+ Metformin	12.95 \pm 0.61 ^c	6.15 \pm 0.13 ^{bc}	9.61 \pm 0.33 ^c	23.52 \pm 1.17 ^a

Units are expressed as mg/g wet tissue. Values are given as mean \pm S.E.M [n=6]. One-way ANOVA followed by post hoc test LSD. Means with different superscript letters within the same column differ significantly at $p < 0.05$.

Table 4 shows the effect of oral treatment with Met - Res - Aldehyde complex on the levels of Total cholesterol, triglycerides, free fatty acids and phospholipids in the renal tissues of experimental groups of rats. The levels were significantly elevated in the diabetic group of rats when compared with the control group of rats. However, the oral administration of Met-Res- Aldehyde complex to diabetic group of rats significantly lowered the levels to near normalcy.

Table-4: The levels of Total Cholesterol, Triglycerides, Free fatty acids (FFA) and Phospholipids in renal tissues of control and experimental groups of rats

Groups	Total Cholesterol	Triglycerides	Free fatty acids	Phospholipids
Control	5.18 \pm 0.11 ^a	5.13 \pm 0.09 ^a	4.51 \pm 0.17 ^a	20.93 \pm 0.46 ^a
Diabetic	15.61 \pm 0.90 ^b	8.86 \pm 0.29 ^b	15.31 \pm 0.25 ^b	32.21 \pm 1.00 ^b
Diabetic + Met-Res- Aldehyde complex	9.7 \pm 0.47 ^c	6.2 \pm 0.12 ^a	10.41 \pm 0.55 ^c	21.25 \pm 0.57 ^a
Diabetic + Metformin	10.75 \pm 0.37 ^c	7.75 \pm 0.45 ^b	12.28 \pm 0.41 ^d	22.00 \pm 0.56 ^a

Units are expressed as mg/g wet tissue. Values are given as mean \pm S.E.M [n=6]. One-way ANOVA followed by post hoc test LSD. Means with different superscript letters within the same column differ significantly at $p < 0.05$.

The effect of oral administration of Met-Res - Aldehyde complex on the levels of serum lipoproteins, such as HDL, LDL and VLDL, in experimental groups of rats was illustrated in Table 5. The levels of LDL and VLDL were elevated

significantly with a concomitant decline in the levels of HDL in the diabetic group of rats compared to that of the control group of rats. These altered levels of serum lipoproteins in the diabetic group of rats were significantly normalized upon treatment with Met-Res- Aldehyde complex.

Table-5: The levels of HDL -cholesterol, LDL-cholesterol and VLDL-cholesterol in serum of control and experimental groups of rats.

Groups	HDL - Cholesterol	LDL-Cholesterol	VLDL - Cholesterol
Control	44.04 \pm 1.36 ^a	55.73 \pm 4.13 ^a	14.21 \pm 0.37 ^a
Diabetic	18.20 \pm 0.68 ^b	161.46 \pm 8.71 ^b	34.86 \pm 1.22 ^b
Diabetic + Met- Res - Aldehyde complex	41.78 \pm 0.99 ^a	60.76 \pm 3.22 ^a	20.6 \pm 0.96 ^c
Diabetic + Metformin	40.43 \pm 0.37 ^a	75.433 \pm 4.32 ^a	24.1 \pm 1.71 ^c

Units are expressed as mg/dL. Values are given as mean \pm S.E.M [n=6]. One-way ANOVA followed by post hoc test LSD. Means with different superscript letters within the same column differ significantly at $p < 0.05$.

The levels of adipokines such as adiponectin and leptin in the plasma are depicted in table 6. The level of plasma adiponectin is reduced, whereas the concentration of leptin is significantly increased in

diabetic group of rats when compared to the control group of rats. Upon treatment with Met - Res - Aldehyde complex, the altered levels were brought back to near normal levels in diabetic rats.

Table-6: The levels of Adiponectin and Leptin in plasma of control and Experimental groups of rats.

Groups	Adiponectin	Leptin
Control	7.2 \pm 0.59 ^a	0.91 \pm 0.13 ^a
Diabetic	3.46 \pm 0.56 ^b	1.58 \pm 0.15 ^b
Diabetic + Met-Res- Aldehyde complex	5.38 \pm 0.19 ^{ac}	0.95 \pm 0.09 ^a
Diabetic + Metformin	4.10 \pm 0.47 ^{bc}	0.82 \pm 0.13 ^a

Units are expressed as μ g/ml for Adiponectin and ng/l for leptin. Values are given as mean \pm S.E.M for groups of six rats in each. One-way ANOVA followed by post hoc test LSD. Means with different superscript letters within the same column differ significantly at $p < 0.05$.

DISCUSSION

High-fat diet supplementation for two weeks induces insulin resistance in experimental rats. Streptozotocin causes diabetes mellitus in experimental animals due to its higher inductive rate and selective pancreatic β -cell toxicity through increased generation of free radicals [94,73]. After intraperitoneal or intravenous administration, STZ

enters the pancreatic β -cells through the Glucose Transporter Protein 2 (GLUT2) which is abundantly present in pancreatic β -cells. Inside the β -cells, STZ causes irreversible cell death via DNA methylation, which depletes the production of insulin [69, 95]. Insulin deficiency disrupts the metabolism of carbohydrates, fats, and proteins in the liver, adipose, and muscle tissue, thereby increasing the levels of glucose, cholesterol, nitrogen balance,

muscle wasting, and weight loss [96, 97]. High-fat diet fed- low dose STZ-induced experimental diabetes mellitus has been widely employed in the recent past due to the existence of chronic hyperglycemia associated with insulin resistance, hypertriglyceridemia, and other clinical as well as biochemical derangements similar to human diabetes mellitus. [98,99].

Diabetes mellitus is essentially characterized by chronic hyperglycemia, which arises due to insufficient insulin secretion coupled with insulin resistance, resulting in disturbances in the metabolism of lipids, carbohydrates, and proteins, in addition to extensive damage to insulin-producing β -cells of the pancreas through increased oxidative stress [100,101]. The pivotal goal of managing diabetes mellitus is to optimize the control of blood glucose levels, reduce the effects of oxidative stress, and regulate the disturbances in lipid metabolism that could predispose patients to cardiovascular complications. Persistent hyperlipidemia, hypercholesterolemia, and hypertriglyceridemia are the terms often used to denote the abnormalities associated with chronic hyperglycemia in T2DM, which in turn essentially arises due to the development of insulin resistance in peripheral tissues coupled with insufficient insulin secretion from the β -cells of the pancreas [102,103].

Lipids are one of the four main biological molecules of the human body, along with carbohydrates, proteins, and nucleic acids. Lipids are essential components of life on a cellular level. They are involved in multiple processes, such as storing energy, serving as chemical messengers, forming cell membranes, and transporting fat-soluble vitamins such as vitamin E. For lipids to carry out these essential roles in the cell, they must travel to their destination cells after being absorbed in the gastrointestinal tract. Without lipoproteins, this transport would not be possible, as the hydrophilic environment of blood is not compatible with the hydrophobic nature of lipids such as cholesterol. Therefore, lipoproteins play an integral role in the human body's ability to utilize lipids, and the metabolism of these lipoproteins directly affects lipid levels in the serum and subsequent lipid processes within cells.

Lipid abnormalities in patients with T2DM are twice as common as in the non-diabetic individuals because of the close link between central obesity, insulin resistance, and chronic hyperglycemia. It is estimated that 30-60% of patients with T2DM have dyslipidemia [104,105]. Diabetic dyslipidemia is a cluster of plasma lipids and lipoprotein abnormalities that are metabolically interrelated, and it is principally characterized by low HDL-C and increased total cholesterol, LDL-C, and TGs levels and is a major cause of cardiovascular problems. [106,107]. Dyslipidemia is more complex in T2DM than observed in individuals with T1DM because LDL-Cholesterol levels are usually within the physiological level with controlled T1DM (Cholesterol Treatment Trialists, 2010) [108,109].

Hyperlipidemia is mainly characterized by increased levels of total cholesterol (TC), triglycerides (TGs), free fatty acids (FFAs), phospholipids (PLs), and alterations in the levels of plasma lipoproteins, which are considered potential risk factors for cardiovascular complications [110,111]. Inadequate utilization of glucose in diabetic models or in diabetic patients due to insufficient / resistance to insulin action stimulates the mobilization of storage of lipids, increasing cholesterol, free fatty acid, and triglycerides levels, which in turn increase the risk for hypertension and microinfarcts, among other alterations [112,113]. Dyslipidemia was defined as a lipid profile that consists of the following abnormalities, either singly or in combination. These include TC- 200 mg/DL, TG levels - 150 mg/DL, HDL- C -40mg/DL, and LDL-C- 100mg/DL [114,115].

Cholesterol is a decorated, high molecular weight sterol. It is an important component of the cell membranes, including organelle membranes inside the cell [116,117]. Elevated levels of cholesterol is an important risk factor responsible for coronary heart diseases. The degree of hypercholesterolemia is directly proportional to the severity of diabetes. An increase in the hepatic cholesterol levels might be due to an increase in the transport of chylomicron cholesterol to the liver [118,119]. So far, thirteen Nobel Prizes have been awarded to celebrities who dedicated major parts of their life careers to cholesterol research [120]. Cholesterol is essential to

build and maintain fluidity over a wide range of temperatures [121,122]. Dietary cholesterol constitutes about 20% of total cholesterol, while the remaining 80% is newly synthesized by *de novo* synthesis [123,124]. Altogether, about 900 mg of cholesterol is synthesized in the liver and central nervous system per day and is excreted as bile salts, which are liver-mediated since mammals are unable to hydrolyse cholesterol [125,126].

Cholesterol synthesis begins with acetyl-CoA, which is derived from amino acids, fats, and carbohydrates. Thereafter, a series of enzymatic reactions occurs, divided into four main steps, each with unique products. The process starts with mevalonate. Second, it transforms into activated isoprenes. The third step is where squalene is produced, and the fourth and last step is where cholesterol forms. 3-hydroxy-3-methylglutaryl-CoA reductase (HMG-CoA reductase) catalyzes the formation of mevalonate, a critical enzyme reaction in cholesterol biosynthesis and the rate-limiting step. HMG-CoA reductase is the major target of statins to lower high LDL-cholesterol [127,128].

Diabetes is known to be associated with an increase in the synthesis of cholesterol, which may be due to increased activity of HMG-CoA reductase, the rate-limiting enzyme in cholesterol synthesis [129,130] and it is the enzymatic step that has been used as the prime pharmacological target of antidiabetic treatments [131]. To perform its various important functions in the body, cholesterol is transported from the liver to the cells, tissues, and glands on low-density lipoprotein carriers. Reverse cholesterol transport from the cells and tissues to the liver is facilitated via high-density lipoprotein carriers [132]. An increase in the hepatic and renal cholesterol levels during chronic hyperglycemia might be due to an increase of cholesterol biosynthesis as well as reduced reverse cholesterol transport [133,134].

Hypercholesterolemia and hypertriglyceridemia are the major risk factors that arise due to chronic hyperglycemia in diabetes, which often results in the initiation, progression, and development of coronary heart disease, a major secondary complication of diabetes mellitus. Cholesterol (both free and esterified forms) and triglycerides are the two main lipids in

plasma. Triglycerides, also known as triacylglycerol, are the major form of fat stored in the body, comprising three fatty acid molecules attached to a single glycerol backbone [135, 136]. Triglycerides ingested from the food are broken down to free fatty acids in the small intestine and enter the bloodstream for transportation to various tissues where they are oxidized to generate energy in the form of ATP. Unused calories derived from fat are converted to triglycerides. Lipases are fat-splitting enzymes found in the blood, gastric juice, pancreatic secretion, intestinal juices, and adipose tissues. Free fatty acids produced by the lipolytic process serve as an important energy source during prolonged fasting and high energy demands [137,138]. Lipolysis primarily takes place in the adipose tissue. The resultant fatty acids produced are oxidized by β -oxidation into acetyl-CoA, which is used by the Krebs cycle. Enzymes like adipose triglyceride lipase (ATGL) and hormone-sensitive lipase (HSL) catalyze the process of lipolysis, which takes place in the cytoplasm. In the gut, pancreatic lipase hydrolyzes dietary triglycerides into fatty acids. Triglycerides are also synthesized by esterification of fatty acids to glycerol, which takes place in the endoplasmic reticulum of the cells [139,140].

Free fatty acids are hydrophobic molecules, which play a crucial role as components of lipids and fats. FFAs are considered the building blocks of fat in the body. The structural variability of FFAs is based on the length of the hydrocarbon chain as well as the presence or absence of double bonds. Accordingly, the properties and functions of FFAs may vary. The carboxylic acid group at the end of the chain is essential for their integration into larger lipid structures like TGs and phospholipids, which form the primary structure of cell membranes. FFAs are more reactive than TGs due to their molecular independence. FFAs play dual roles in the body. On one hand, FFA oxidation in mitochondria releases immediate energy in the form of ATP during prolonged fasting and severe exercise. On the other hand, excess FFAs in the bloodstream can be harmful, contributing to the development of lipotoxicity, insulin resistance, and systemic inflammation. However, the impact of FFAs largely depends on their nature and levels. While TGs serve as a long-term

energy source, FFAs act as immediate energy substrates [141,142].

The various sources of FFAs include dietary intake, endogenous production, and stored lipids. FFAs are released as a result of the breakdown of TGs, and the process is a vital part of energy generation cycles, especially in circumstances where carbohydrates are inadequate. They act as a major source of endogenous energy for pancreatic β -cells and are capable of freely diffusing through the plasma membrane. Free fatty acids play an important role in the development of insulin resistance. Elevated levels of FFAs are often observed in conditions such as obesity, T2DM, and cardiovascular diseases [143,144]. Obesity is associated with increased FFA levels. FFA inhibits the anti-lipolytic effect of insulin. High levels of FFAs rather than just TG are often associated with insulin resistance and fatty liver. FFAs can impair insulin signalling, promote inflammation, and contribute to lipotoxicity in non-adipose tissues. In signal transduction, FFAs function as secondary messengers. FFAs play a central role in lipid metabolism, which includes the synthesis and breakdown of TGs, phospholipids, and cholesterol. In the bloodstream, FFAs are bound to albumin, which facilitates their solubility and delivery to target tissues. FFAs aid in the absorption of fat-soluble vitamins such as vitamins A, D, E and K [145,146].

Adipose tissue, which stores the body fat, serves as a reservoir for FFAs. Circulating FFAs are primarily derived from the cleavage of triacylglycerol (TAG) of fat deposits by enzymes, notably fatty triacylglycerol lipase and hormone-sensitive lipase [147,148]. In the liver, the excess free fatty acids stimulate the production of glucose through gluconeogenesis and glucose output, which essentially contribute to the development of increased fasting blood glucose levels and the onset of diabetes [149,150]. Insulin triggers lipoprotein lipase, which can metabolize TGs and VLDL-C. In diabetic patients, lipoprotein lipase is less active due to insulin deficiency, which promotes the conversion of free fatty acids into phospholipids and cholesterol, and this can lead to increased levels of phospholipids in serum [151,152]. Accumulation of FFA and TG in the pancreatic β -cells have a pessimistic effect on β -cell function, resulting from increased pressure to secrete more insulin, which

leads to β -cell deterioration up to apoptosis [153, 154].

Experimental evidence suggests that the elevated FFA levels inhibit the translocation of glucose transporter 4 (GLUT4) in the muscle, which is the major site of total glucose utilization in the body [155,156]. Free fatty acids (FFAs) released from the adipocytes serve as the prime source of fuel in the post-absorptive state. Plasma FFA levels reflect a balance between release from the intravascular lipolysis of triglyceride-rich lipoproteins and the uptake of FFA, predominantly re-esterified in adipose tissue as well as in the liver and oxidized in muscle, heart, liver, and other tissues. Thus, the levels of FFAs released from the adipose tissues can be considered as a marker for insulin resistance [157,158]. Thus, measuring FFAs provides insights into lipid mobilization, insulin resistance, and metabolic dysregulation [159,160]. FFAs can be quantitatively estimated in serum, plasma, and tissue samples.

The major source of fuel for oxidative muscles such as heart and skeletal muscles are free fatty acids. FFAs also reduce insulin sensitivity in muscle by inhibiting insulin-mediated glucose uptake, and FFA flux to the liver is associated with the increased production of TG-rich VLDL-C [161,162]. Due to the lack of insulin secretion, TG levels will be increased, which promotes the process of conversion of HDL into LDL and accelerates the excretion of HDL [163,164]. LDL is a major risk factor for atherosclerotic CVD, including coronary artery disease in T2DM patients [165,166]. In several studies, it was found that there is a high prevalence of dyslipidemia among women with diabetes due to the increased level of adipose tissue in the abdomen; it releases a high amount of FFA. The enhanced flux of FFAs to the liver chiefly contributes to dyslipidemia by facilitating the excessive production of VLDL and TG [167,168].

Increased free fatty acid flux from adipose tissue to non-adipose tissues, especially the liver, resulting from abnormalities of fat metabolism, participates in increased synthesis and secretion of VLDL. High plasma concentrations of triglyceride-rich lipoprotein and VLDL lead to an increase in the release of FFAs and generation of remnants as a result of lipolysis by the enzyme lipoprotein lipase. The increased VLDL

level down regulates the LDL receptor [169,170] resulting in an increased proportion of LDL cholesterol particles [171], decreased HDL cholesterol level, and elevated peripheral TG concentrations [172,173].

Phospholipids (PLs) are indispensable molecules fundamental for maintaining the function, structure, and regulation of cells and tissues throughout the body. The endoplasmic reticulum (ER) is the primary site for phospholipid synthesis and also accounts for >60% of phospholipid mass in a variety of cell types. At the same time, the phospholipid content and composition of the ER are in constant flux owing to constitutive and regulated export to other organelles and secretion of lipids to the extracellular environment by specialized cells such as hepatocytes, intestinal epithelial cells, and macrophages. Lipid biosynthetic capacity must match these export demands in order to maintain ER integrity and the membrane requirements of distal organelles. The extended tubular and planar ER network extends to all regions of the cell, where it interfaces at membrane contact sites with the plasma membrane, mitochondria, and Golgi apparatus for the purpose of lipid transfer, integration of metabolic pathways, and calcium homeostasis. In this context, it is increasingly apparent that phospholipid synthesis in the ER is spatially integrated with the structure and function of other organelles, which in turn can be negatively impacted by disturbances in ER function [174-177].

PLs are crucial components of cell membranes, serving various essential functions in maintaining cellular structure and function. The structure of phospholipids gives them an amphiphilic nature, with hydrophilic head groups and hydrophobic tails, which allow PLs to form lipid bilayers in aqueous environments, such as cell membranes, thus forming a stable barrier that separates the interior of cells from their external surroundings. Phospholipids contribute to the characteristic inner and outer membranes that give them their shape [178,179]. Moreover, diverse combinations of head groups and fatty acids give rise to a multitude of phospholipid species, each exhibiting unique properties and functions in biological processes and membrane integrity. The primary role of phospholipids is to form the lipid bilayer, the basic structural framework of all cell

membranes [180,181]. This bilayer provides a semi-permeable barrier that separates the internal cellular environment from the external surroundings, allowing for compartmentalization and regulation of cellular processes [182,183]. Phospholipids help maintain membrane fluidity and stability, which are crucial for the proper functioning of membrane-bound proteins, ion channels, and transporters. By modulating the fluidity of cell membranes, they also influence cell signaling, adhesion, and migration processes. Phospholipids also serve as an energy reservoir, thereby aiding in maintaining energy homeostasis and executing essential metabolic functions [184,185]. Above all, PLs assume critical functions across various organ systems, notably in the nervous system, where they are indispensable for the formation and functionality of myelin sheaths [186,187]. These sheaths serve to insulate nerve fibers, facilitating the rapid conduction of nerve impulses.

Beyond their intracellular roles, phospholipids play integral roles in systemic physiological processes within multicellular organisms. Notably, phospholipids are vital constituents of lipoproteins [188,189], which serve as carriers for lipid transport throughout the bloodstream. Lipoproteins, including low-density lipoprotein and high-density lipoprotein, facilitate the transport of cholesterol and other lipids to and from peripheral tissues, thereby contributing significantly to lipid metabolism and overall lipid homeostasis [190,191]. Metabolites of phospholipids also play important roles in cell signaling, intracellular communication, and regulation of membrane protein function and various cellular processes. For example, phosphatidylinositol (PI) is a precursor for second messengers involved in signal transduction cascades, such as phosphatidylinositol 4, 5-bisphosphate (PIP₂). PIP₂ is cleaved by phospholipase C to generate inositol trisphosphate and diacylglycerol, which regulate intracellular calcium levels and protein kinase C activation, respectively [192,193]. Lysophosphatidic acid (LPA) can activate intracellular signaling pathways involved in promoting cell proliferation, survival, and adipocyte differentiation, thereby influencing overall energy metabolism and adipose tissue function [194,195]. Furthermore, the fatty acids of phospholipids serve as critical precursors for numerous biologically active molecules via

enzymatic and non-enzymatic pathways [196,197]. Released fatty acids also serve as substrates for enzymatic reactions, generating bioactive lipid species involved in cell signaling, inflammation, and immune regulation [198,199]. Thus, the fatty acid components of phospholipids play multifaceted roles in the body's physiological processes, beyond their structural functions.

The multifaceted functions provided by phospholipids underscore their significance in preserving cellular homeostasis and supporting myriad physiological processes. Notably, phospholipids play a pivotal role in cellular and mitochondrial physiology. Alterations in these functions can implicate various diseases; for instance, oxidized phospholipids are associated with atherosclerosis and non-alcoholic steatohepatitis [200,201]. Diseases such as cancer, diabetes, cardiovascular, and infectious diseases have been linked to changes in phospholipid composition, distribution, and metabolism [202,203]. Additionally, defects in nuclear genes can lead to phospholipid metabolism disorders, particularly in mitochondrial diseases like Barth syndrome and dilated cardiomyopathy [204,205]. Recent investigations suggest that alterations in phospholipids, particularly within mitochondria, may significantly contribute to brain dysfunction following cardiac arrest [206,207].

Phospholipids constitute the vital part of biomembranes rich in polyunsaturated fatty acids, which are susceptible substrates for free radicals. The elevated plasma phospholipid levels are a consequence of elevated levels of lipoproteins. The plasma total cholesterol/phospholipids ratio is one of the important markers for the development of atherosclerosis [208,209]. The restoration of phospholipid levels by the newly synthesized complex may be due to the restricted mobilization of plasma triglycerides, regulating the tissue metabolism and improving the level of insulin secretion and its action, presumably mediating cholesterol and phospholipids.

The observed increase in the levels of vital components of lipid metabolism such as total cholesterol, triglycerides, free fatty acids, and phospholipids in the diabetic group of rats are mainly due to the increased transport of fatty acids as a result

of their excessive mobilization, which in turn promotes the synthesis of phospholipids and cholesteryl esters by the liver and kidney. Met-Res-Aldehyde complex treatment of diabetic rats reduces the levels of liver and kidney free fatty acids and thereby alleviates diabetic dyslipidemia. Further, the elevated levels of plasma lipids in diabetic group of rats are essentially due to an increase in the mobilization of free fatty acids from the peripheral depots since insulin inhibits the activity of hormone-sensitive lipase. Treatment with the newly synthesized complex in a diabetic group of rats resulted in the amelioration of hyperlipidemia, and this may be primarily attributed to the enhanced glucose utilization [60].

In humans, cholesterol circulates as a component of plasma lipoproteins in the range of 150-250mg/dL. Lipoproteins are complex molecules that involve several different components. They contain a central core made of triglycerides and cholesterol esters [210,211]. Fatty acids released from triglycerides can be used for energy storage or production, and cholesterol is critical for steroid synthesis, cellular membrane formation, and bile acid production. Surrounding this core is a mix of phospholipids, free cholesterol, and apolipoproteins (apo). The apolipoproteins are particularly important, as they play a role in classifying lipoproteins into five main classes: chylomicrons, very-low-density lipoprotein (VLDL), intermediate-density lipoprotein (IDL), low-density lipoprotein (LDL), and high-density lipoprotein (HDL). They provide structure and function in lipid metabolism. The differentiation between these classes depends on the size of the molecule, its lipid content, and the type of apolipoprotein it features. HDL, colloquially known as "good cholesterol," participates in reverse cholesterol transport, while LDL, colloquially known as "bad cholesterol," promotes atherosclerosis.

Any impairment in lipoprotein metabolism could lead to catastrophic implications in an affected individual. A pathologic increase in LDL, for example, is a known risk factor for cardiovascular disease, as it leads to premature atherosclerotic changes in vessels. Lipid abnormalities are not just quantitative, which means measuring the particular lipoproteins, but also qualitative, which measures the particle

factors like density and size of the particles. The characteristic features of diabetic dyslipidemia, which aggravate the lipid accumulation in the arterial wall and the formation of atherosclerotic plaques, are increased triglycerides, small dense LDL cholesterol, and low HDL cholesterol levels [212, 213]. Triglyceride-rich lipoproteins such as chylomicrons and VLDL-cholesterol mediate the delivery of TGs to the peripheral tissues, while LDL-cholesterol transports cholesterol to peripheral tissues [214,215]. Atherogenic dyslipidemia is one of the major risk factors for CVD in diabetic patients. An increased level of VLDL particles in T2DM leads to the generation of atherogenic remnants [216,217]. Remnants are cholesterol-rich particles that are small enough to penetrate the vessel wall, and thus, they are considered to be atherogenic lipoproteins. Multiple mechanisms are responsible for the dyslipidemia observed in patients with T2DM, which is affected both by the level of glucose control and by factors such as central obesity and inflammation that also contribute to dyslipidemia.

Lipoprotein metabolism is largely influenced by lipid transfer proteins (LTP). Among these, two play an important role: cholesterol ester transfer protein (CETP) and phospholipid transfer protein (PLTP). Cholesteryl ester transfer protein (CETP) promotes the transfer of cholesteryl esters from HDL to apoB-containing lipoproteins, including VLDL, VLDL remnant, IDL, and LDL, in exchange for triglycerides. As a result, HDL cholesterol decreases, and cholesterol content in VLDL increases [218,219]. Subsequently, it is returned to the liver and endocytosed by hepatocytes via scavenger receptors. HDL can then be excreted or recycled by the Golgi apparatus [220, 221]. PLTP facilitates the transfer of phospholipids between lipoproteins. Any modification of CETP or PLTP activities is likely to promote significant qualitative abnormalities of lipoproteins. A significant increase in PLTP activity has been reported in T2DM [222, 223]. In addition to the above regulatory proteins, insulin controls hepatic sterol regulatory element-binding protein (SREBP) expression, which is a key transcription factor responsible for regulating fatty acid and cholesterol biosynthesis. SREBP can activate a cascade of enzymes involved in the cholesterol biosynthetic pathways, such as HMG-CoA reductase and fatty acid

synthase [224,225]. Expression of SREBP is increased by insulin in all three major insulin target tissues, namely the liver, adipose, and skeletal muscles [226]. Similarly, levels of SREBP are enhanced in the presence of hyperinsulinemia [227,228].

HDL-cholesterol is a small, spherical lipoprotein secreted by the hepatocytes and small intestine as small, lipid-poor lipoproteins. HDL-c removes excess cholesterol from arteries, the liver, and other tissues and transports it to the liver and other steroidogenic tissues for metabolism and excretion [229-231]. Lecithin-cholesterol acyl transferase (LCAT) is an enzyme that is responsible for transporting surplus cholesterol back to HDL molecules. There is evidence that even some oxidized LDL can be removed by the LCAT and HDL-cholesterol and hence HDL-c is considered good cholesterol [232,233]. With the enrichment of HDL-c with cholesterol esters, they become more spherical, larger, and more buoyant. The triglycerides will be removed from the HDL-c particles when they pass through the liver through the action of Hepatic Triglyceride Lipase (HTGL). The nascent HDL particle is mostly composed of phospholipids and proteins. The optimal activity of lipoprotein lipase activity is absolutely necessary for the formation of HDL-c, and a decrease in lipoprotein lipase activity may lead to a decrease in HDL-c levels [234,235]. Thus, the HDL particles that exit from the liver have a decreased neutral lipid content and can accept more cholesterol ester, and this scheme for the metabolism of cholesterol is referred to as reverse cholesterol transport (RCT). Thus, the major HDL-c functions are esterification of cholesterol and reverse cholesterol transport, in which cholesterol from the cells is excreted in the bile. HDL-c also has several other anti-atherogenic functions, which mainly include antioxidative, vasodilation, anti-inflammatory, anti-apoptotic, anti-thrombotic, and anti-infectious [236, 237].

LDL-cholesterol is often known as "bad cholesterol" because excess LDL-c contributes to plaque formation in the arteries. LDL-c makes up most of the body's cholesterol. Small LDL particles are more atherogenic than large LDL [238,239]. LDL-cholesterol is a leading cause of atherosclerotic cardiovascular disease (ASCVD); this involves many

processes that ultimately result in ASCVD. LDL accumulates in circulating macrophages following modifications, such as oxidation. Oxidized LDL acts as a chemoattractant for monocytes, which then differentiate into macrophages. These macrophages become trapped in the vessel wall, likely due to abnormal endothelial leukocyte adhesion molecule-1, vascular cell adhesion molecule-1, and intercellular adhesion molecule-1 [240, 241]. The LDL particle promotes an inflammatory response, leading to increased cytokine and antibody levels. The modified LDL in macrophages, now called foam cells, has the potential to rupture, releasing oxidized LDL, enzymes, and free radicals that can further damage the vessel wall [242,243]. Additionally, the modified LDL impairs nitric oxide release due to dysfunctional endothelial function. This process reduces the vessel's ability to vasodilate appropriately. Lastly, oxidized LDL causes increased platelet aggregation and thromboxane release. The net result is that platelet activity and aggregation become enhanced [244 -246]. Statins have an indirect effect on lipoprotein metabolism. The mechanism of action involves competitive inhibition of HMG-CoA reductase, the rate-limiting enzyme in cholesterol biosynthesis in the liver. As the liver senses a decrease in cholesterol production, it attempts to compensate by increasing the number of LDL receptors on its cells, leading to increased uptake of LDL and VLDL into the liver, which then metabolizes them into cholesterol and other molecules. Statins effectively reduce circulating LDL and VLDL levels, thereby decreasing cholesterol deposition in tissues [247,248]. Other medications include ezetimibe and PCSK9 inhibitors, in addition to statins, to lower LDL-C by more than 50%, especially in high-risk patients. Newer drugs targeting cholesterol and lipoprotein metabolism are critical for managing or preventing ASCVD.

Adipose tissue, despite being a lipid storage site, also functions as a paracrine and endocrine organ that secretes adipocytokines such as leptin, adiponectin, and proinflammatory cytokines, which possess atherogenic effects contributing to adverse metabolic and cardiovascular risk factors [249-251]. An increase in visceral adiposity is associated with cardiometabolic risk and increased risk of developing coronary heart disease and type 2 DM.

Adipokines are proteins secreted by the adipocytes that are known to have direct or indirect regulation of insulin sensitivity [252]. Leptin and adiponectin ameliorate hyperglycemia in animal models of T2DM [253]. Adiponectin possesses an insulin-sensitizing effect. The downregulation of adiponectin leads to insulin resistance, resulting in type 2 diabetes. Improving adiponectin levels ameliorates insulin resistance, which decreases the risk factors of diabetes. The fatty acid oxidation by adiponectin improves insulin sensitivity and facilitates glucose uptake in skeletal muscle. Leptin inhibits appetite, stimulates thermogenesis, and decreases the plasma glucose and triglyceride levels, resulting in a reduction in body weight. Chronic hyperglycemia-induced leptin resistance results in fat accumulation in type 2 diabetes mellitus. The level of plasma adiponectin is reduced, whereas the concentration of leptin is significantly increased in diabetic rats compared with control rats. The modulation of the pathophysiology of diabetes induced by adiponectin may be due to the increase in glucose uptake mediated by AMPK activation that stimulates phosphorylation of the downstream target of AKT, thereby increasing the translocation of the GLUT-4 transporters [254,255].

In the present study, HFD-STZ-induced diabetic rats showed significantly elevated levels of FFA, total cholesterol, and triglycerides in plasma and liver and kidney as well as increased levels of plasma LDL-cholesterol and VLDL-cholesterol and decreased HDL-cholesterol. Oral administration of Met-Res-Aldehyde complex to diabetic rats significantly reversed the altered levels of lipid profiles in plasma as well as in vital tissues when compared to diabetic rats. The antidyslipidemic efficacy was comparable with metformin treatment in the experimental diabetic group of rats. The anti-dyslipidemic property of Met-Res-Aldehyde complex might be due to the increased uptake and oxidation of fatty acids as a result of enhanced activation of AMPK in peripheral tissues, especially in skeletal muscles.

CONCLUSION

The alterations in the levels of total lipids, triglycerides, free fatty acids, phospholipids, and lipoproteins in high-fat diet fed- low dose

streptozotocin-induced experimental Type 2 diabetic rats were restored to near-physiological range by the oral administration of the newly synthesized Met-Res-Aldehyde complex, which indicates the antidyslipidemic property of the complex. The observed antidyslipidemic property of the complex might be due to the insulin stimulatory/mimetic efficacy of the Met-Res-Aldehyde complex.

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